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COMMITMENT IN NIGERIAN LITERATURE: A STUDY OF NWACHUKWU-

AGBADA'S *PRAYER BEADS OF A SILENT SUPPLICANT*

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Abstract

Commitment in literature is a conscious engagement of writers with the socio-political, cultural and economic realities of their environments. These writers use literature as a tool for advocacy and social transformation. Commitment in modern African literature began with cultural activism associated with the colonial era and progressed to the disillusionment of the post-independence era. It is a veritable ideology that highlights a writer's belief in an egalitarian society and has become a means through which writers participate in nation-building. Commitment in art has established writers as critical thinkers, philosophers and clairvoyants of their societies. Achebe, for instance, published *A Man of the People* and shortly afterwards, Nigeria's first military coup took place. In his *Prayer Beads of the Silent Suppliant* (2005), J.O. J. Nwachukwu-Agbada, a professor of Literature expands the epistemic boundaries of literature of commitment in Africa. The collection has 78 poems written on varied issues in Africa. The paper selects four verses from the anthology due to the constraints of time and space – poems which profoundly justify the poet as a committed writer. The Reflectionist theory – the idea that literature reflects the social, political, cultural, economic and ethical realities of the society that produced it – has been applied in the analysis of the poems. The methodology of the research is qualitative – requiring close reading, analysis and interrogation of selected poems. The research findings highlight Nwachukwu-Agbada as a socially committed writer who makes extensive use of of metaphor, rhetorical question, parallelism, repetition, irony and sarcasm to describe the inept leadership of the Nigerian society, which is complicit in the social inequalities in the land.

Key Words: Commitment, African Literature, Reflectionist theory, Cultural activism, Disillusionment

Conceptual Premise

Commitment in literature refers to the strategic engagement of writers with the socio-political, cultural and economic realities of their environments. These writers use literature as a tool for advocacy and social transformation. This tradition emerged in the colonial and post— independence eras of Nigerian literature and mirrors a writer’s role in nation-building and cultural reclamation. The historiography of literature of commitment in Nigeria is traceable to the publication of Chinua Achebe’s *Things Fall Apart* (1958) in mid-20th century, influenced primarily by the anti-colonial struggle and cultural activism. There is also Wole Soyinka’s *A Dance of the Forest* (1960) which shows a writer’s commitment to nation-building and cultural struggle by satirising neo-colonialism.

In African literature, commitment is the African writer’s dedication to addressing social and political realities of their society. It contradicts the idea of art-for-art’s sake to deploy literature as an instrument of change, awareness and resistance. The colonial era ignited the momentum of commitment in African literature. African writers saw themselves as the voice of the people, speaking against exploitation, corruption and neo-colonialism.

The colonial period in African literature had writers such as Chinua Achebe, Wole Soyinka and Ngugi wa Thiongo, among others. Gikandi (2013, p. 54) avers that “Modern African literature was produced in the crucible of colonialism. The first generation African writers felt a responsibility of addressing the distorted African image propagated by the colonial writers. There was Ngugi wa Thiongo who used fiction to denounce neo-colonialism and political corruption, while advocating social revolution. According to Lindfors (2013, p. 27), “Ngugi was one of the first in East Africa to wake up and write a serious indictment of the turn his nation had taken.” Ousman Sembene uses literature to inspire social resistance in his *God’s Bits of Wood*. There are literatures of commitment

for gender equality and justice as propagated by Buchi Emecheta in her *Second Class Citizen* and more recently by Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's *The Purple Hibiscus*.

Commitment in African literature emphasises a writer's responsibility to his society, as well as mirrors the social realities in the society with the aim of instigating a change. Through the literature of commitment, writers educate and inspire the people in relevant subject matters of social justice, social responsibility, gender equality and environmental degradation, among others.

Literature of commitment is akin to the literature of revolutionary thought or aesthetics. Udentia (1993, xix) views this type of literature as that which "advocates for a radical break with our colonial past and a revolutionary replacement of its structures with genuine people-oriented ones." Besides Achebe's *No Longer at Ease* and *A Man of the People*, Soyinka's *The Interpreters*, *A Dance of the Forest*, *The Trial of Brother Jero*, Ngugi wa Thiongo's *Petals of Blood*; there were also Alex La Guma's *In the Fog of the Season's End*, Festus Iyayi's *Violence*, Sahle Sellasie's *The Afresta*, Tuden Fatunde's *No Food, No Country*, Femis Osofisan's *Morountodun*, *No More the Wasted Breed*, Tess Onwueme's *The Desert Encroaches*, among others.

This paper is predicated on the Reflectionist theory, a concept in literary criticism with the core idea that art reflects the realities, values and ethos of its time. The reflectionist theory is an offshoot of the Marxist theory. Karl Heinrich Marx (1818 – 1883) was a German political and philosophical theorist and revolutionist. His ideas have had a long standing impact on the modern history of the world. Habib (2005, p.527) reports that "Until the collapse in 1991 of the Communist systems of the USSR and Eastern Europe, one third of the world's population had been living under political administrations claiming descent from Marx's ideas." Marx fundamentally critiqued the capitalist system. He sought to analyse the structural causes behind capitalist exploitation. He viewed the bourgeoisies as running an imperialist enterprise to impoverish the poor. He adapted the Hegelian Dialectic, which was a way of logically thinking about any circumstance as bearing comprehensive

stages, where each stage supersedes the previous. Hegel's Dialectic was important to Marx because of the former's viewing of the world, human and history as a product of human labour. However, while Hegel viewed the dialectical movement of history as driven by Divinity, Marx views it as driven by class struggle. In fact, he posits in his *The Communist Manifesto* (1848): "The history of all hitherto existing society is the history of class struggles" (Habib, 2005, p. 541). Thus, Marx views all trajectories of human history as driven by class conflict. Marx therefore advocated a time when capitalist mode of production will collapse and give way to socialism.

Marx developed the concept of ideology as the domination of the views of a few who hold state power. Since the view controls the means of production, it is empowered to influence maps of meaning relating to law, morality and culture. A Marxist critic is interested in depicting the inequalities and inequities in the society. He scrutinizes a text to see how there is a manipulation of the worker by the bourgeoisie. He wants to find out the social injustice existing in the society. One of the assumptions of Marxism, says Dobie (2012, p. 9) is that the means of production will always generate conflict between social classes because the bourgeois class who controls the means of production will like to make profit from the labour of the proletariat. Since the economic system shapes the society, the methods of production are known as the base, while the social and ideological systems they generate are called the superstructure. The dominant class controls the superstructure and by extension the working class.

The influence of Marxism, maintains Habib (2005, p. 534), "has been fundamental in challenging the claims of the law to be eternal, or of the bourgeoisie to represent the interests of the nation, of individuality and freedom to be universal." Particularly, the Marxist ideology has been able to identify class struggle as the main force behind historical trajectories and conflicts.

Drawing from the Marxist ideology, Georg Lukacs (1865 – 1971), a Jewish Hungarian philosopher developed the theory of reflectionism. Dobie (2012, p. 85) states that reflectionism assumes "that

a text will reflect the society that produced it.” A reflectionist is interested in closely reading a text to discover the fragmentation and alienation of the society while delineating them as ills of capitalism. When applied to a literature of commitment, reflectionism interrogates the extent to which a text reflects the social imbalances, political corruption and economic inequalities in the society.

Commitment in Nwachukwu’Agbada’s *Prayer Beads of a Silent Suppliant* (2005)

Nwachukwu-Agbada, a professor of literature and prolific creative writer, has shown in his art that he is a socially committed writer. His first anthology of poetry, *Prayer Beads of a Silent Suppliant* (2005) published by John-Jacobs Publishers, has expanded the epistemic boundaries of the literature of commitment. Through the literary devices of metaphor, rhetorical question, parallelism, irony and sarcasm, Nwachukwu-Agbada makes his voice heard as a writer committed to the social well-being of his people. In his “Blind Men”, a three-stanza verse, the poet’s persona interrogates the metaphor of blindness. From the beginning, the persona of the poem asks a rhetorical question: “Who are blind men?” The poem takes the structure of J. p. Clark’s “Casualties” with a recurring use of rhetorical question. The poem “Blind Men” is a metaphor ultimately seeking to unravel the mystery of blindness. The persona adopts an elimination process to determine the metaphor of blindness. Stylistically, the persona asks if blind men are those whose eyes are physically closed:

Who are blind men??
Are they those whose eyes
are forever sealed
and darkness mean the same
Are they those

I see on streets
along with guides
and helpmates and crooked sticks? (p. 13).

The foregoing contains tropes of physical blindness as illustrated with the adjectives of “sealed” and “darkness.” Blindness is a malaise, a physical disability which renders its victims vulnerable and pitiable. There is an evocation of catharsis running in the lines as these blind men have sealed eyes – day and darkness make no sense to them. They are also on the streets with “guides and “crooked sticks” – all symbolic of their helplessness. They are helpless beggars on the streets who are at the mercy of flies:

Who are blind men?
Blind men are not those
whose mouths are often
slipping slime
who mutter a string of nonsense
As in a fiery prayer meet
Whose true companions
Are fruitfly and flea
No, they are not
those who dish out dirges
and cry for coins
even in unsafe spots (pp. 13 – 14).

The catharsis in stanza one is reinforced further in the foregoing lines. The mouths of the blind men in this stanza drool with saliva. They are even deranged as they “mutter a string of nonsense”.

They are also more helpless than those in stanza one because while the former have “help mates” the latter have none. In fact, their “true companions” are “fruitfly and flea”. They seem to be in a melancholic state as they “dish out dirges”. Their condition is both unpleasant and discomforting. They beg and “cry for coins/even in unsafe spots.” Apparently, their condition exposes them to environmental hazards. They are left with no choice than to remain as beggars. The blind men in this case are both physically and mentally challenged.

It is, however, in the last stanza that the poet’s persona resolves the metaphor of the blind men. By so doing he employs the stylistic tool of suspense, while deductively narrowing down on the blind men inferred. This stanza pointedly unravels the metaphor of the blind men and pins the poet as one committed to an egalitarian society:

Blind men are those
who see
the skies and seas
and they try in vain
to pocket them
in their *babaringa*
and *dansikis*
They’re those
who man our collective mint
And turn the country skint
They’re those
who in greed have made
our blooming boys suddenly blind
and our garrulous girls hastily glum (p. 14)

The foregoing excerpt is replete with metaphors and symbols of greed and rapaciousness. The blind men who see “the skies and the seas” are leaders who want to appropriate the entire stretch of resources in the country. Metaphorically, they are blind because they detest the virtues of patriotism and commitment needed for nation-building. They are greedy leaders who steal the commonwealth of the country as symbolised by “skies and seas”. There is also symbolism in the use of “barbaringa” and “dansikis” – long and deep-pocket gowns with which they embezzle the nation’s resources. These resources are symbolised by “our collective mint” which get stolen by the leaders of the people. This act of inhumanity bears down negatively on the youths who are rendered incapacitated. For instance, “our blooming boys suddenly go blind” and “our garrulous girls hastily glum”. The tropes of “blind” and “glum” depict weakness and inactivity. It is not improbable that the youths may have been silenced by bribe and their conscience bought over.

Following the foregoing, the poet’s persona indicts everyone in the metaphysical condition of blindness. When the youths are bought over or the people passively watch as their commonwealth is frittered away, the persona views it as metaphoric blindness:

Blind men are us all
with wholesome eyes
who may not know that our
guides and helpmates
lack the sense of light (p. 14).

The persona obviously expects action from the beleaguered people of his country who condone the excesses of evil leadership. The stand of the persona therefore is that everyone becomes “blind” when no one speaks against the crisis of leadership in the country.

The trajectory of commitment is further evident in Nwachukwu-Agbada's "Aids", a poem which deploys sarcasm to interrogate the propriety of seeking aid from the international community. The poem is a beautiful piece that has the voice of a single speaker. The tone of the poem is reflective and sober. The opening lines of the poem capture the voice of a lonely, dissatisfied speaker seeking elusive answers from the barrage of puzzles bordering on African leaders' penchant for seeking foreign aids and assistance, without working hard at the home front. The 48-line poem begins with a stretch of parallel lines:

We who hanker
after help
across virulent seas
upon dusty winds
traversing sands and reasons
we who are assured
of impregnating this land
with a borrowed penis
we who daily dwell on
debt relief
and pray for debt forgiveness. (p. 38)

The persona angrily characterises African leaders as "beggars" "hankering after help", which is most times elusive. They have to go against the tide of nature on the one hand, and reason on the other. The symbols "virulent seas" and "dusty winds" are evidence of the hazards faced by help-seekers. They also go against the voice of "reason" because as blind as they are, these leaders have failed to look inwards for home-grown solutions. This is why the persona further mocks the leaders who are deluded to believe that the aid they seek is the ultimate solution. He questions the rationale

for a “borrowed penis” to “impregnate” the land – a metaphor for a foreign solution expected to jumpstart the growth of the African land.

The persona further mocks the leaders who hanker for debt relief and still blame others for the underdevelopment of the land. It is ironic that the leaders “dwell on/a debt relief” and still blame their benefactors for “guzzling our goals”. The persona views it as an act of delusion to remain subservient to others to survive.

The persona remains consistent in condemning the leaders’ penchant for aids throughout the poem. In line 15, he wonders why we should “abandon our hoes” only to “scramble for Kalashnikov. The use of “hoes” symbolises agriculture and industry while “Kalashnikov” represents warfare. It shows a poor system where military equipment is prioritised over agricultural industry that will guarantee food security and job creation. The persona reminds the leaders that “forests of war” only “invite famine/into the homestead.”

The aid sought after by African leaders may not be the solution to the myriads of problems bedevilling the continent. The persona views these aids as mere “crumbles from a broken crucible/like a crumb of bread” (p. 38), casting an imagery that is unpleasant. There is a metaphor of brokenness illustrated by the crucible, then there is a simile heightening the sarcasm in the foregoing line as the foreign aid is compared to a leftover on the table. Thus, the loan givers do not aim at developing Africa but to exploit her. Furthermore, it is sad that these leaders beg for aid “with perforated plates” (line 27), implying that more than half of what is realised is unaccounted for and does not actually benefit the masses of the continent.

The persona flays foreign aid donors, characterising them as: “robbers of our resources/ sorcerers (line 32) / who turned our siblings/into slaves/aid our tummies into insatiable tunnels” (p. 39). He wonders if any genuine help could be obtained from people who do not mean well for the continent. The characterisation of these donors as “robbers” is an allusion to the historical partitioning of

Africa by the European imperialists in Berlin and the roguery associated with colonization. They are also called “sorcerers”, another allusion to the devilish role played in the precolonial and colonial period, an era characterised by slavery and subjugation.

Furthermore, the persona interrogates the rationale for seeking aid when countries can work hard and be self-sufficient. In the case of the persona’s country, the leaders practically do nothing with their heads and hands except going out for aids. According to him:

We who head for aid

Amidst unsowing sickles

And unharvesting hoes

Hoping for baked bread

Somewhere (p. 39).

The tone of the foregoing is sarcastic. African leaders go out for aids without any genuine efforts at improving their countries. They unfortunately view “aids” as the ‘low hanging fruits’ which should be plucked at the expense of hard work. The lines show that African leaders’ penchant for foreign aids makes them unable to churn out practical initiatives that propel development. Symbols of laziness and apathy for hard work dot the above lines. There are “unsowing sickles” and “unharvesting hoes” symbolising the abandonment of agriculture and local industry. The persona believes that African leaders can do better by reviving the agricultural industry than “hanker” after aids and foreign help, which may hardly develop a country.

Nwachukwu-Agbada further reinforces his status as a committed writer in his poem “Cycles”, a ten-stanza verse which repudiates the sycophancy associated with poor, inept leadership. The poem, “Cycles”, is a sarcasm which tells a panoramic story of what happens when a man of power visits a place. The first stanza captures a sudden change in the condition of the roads:

Hurriedly repaired roads

widened pathways

trimmed tree branches

beaten-down side kiosks

shoveled hovels

banished beggars (p. 40).

The foregoing lines symbolise a dysfunctional system thriving in superficiality and sycophancy, where visiting leaders are awaited with a high degree of cosmetic preparations which end as soon as the said leaders return to the seat of power. The tone of the poem itself is ostensibly satiric. Work done within the short period of preparation is usually shoddy, lacking depth. Roads are “hurriedly” repaired because there is no sincerity of purpose. Many of these roads cave in shortly after such advertised and showy state visits. The widened pathways and “trimmed” tree branches are made to impress the visiting leader who is also as corrupt as those preparing to receive them. There are images of a filthy city with bad roads and narrow pathways. The trees are also overgrown, only made to attract attention at the visitation of a leader. There are shanties all over the city only “beaten down” at the visit of the leader. The chaotic nature of the city is hidden to impress the visiting leader.

The persona mocks a system which operates in a superficial manner – lacking basic plans of achieving excellence. The cosmetic tone of the poem persists in the second stanza as the mass media is awash with the visit of the “messianic leader”:

Radio jingles

TV announcement

Newstalks

Editorials

Slogans

Buntings

Colours

Banners

“Welcome, the modern Messiah” (p. 40).

The persona satirises a system that invests so much resources in vanities. The paid radio jingles, et cetera, form a significant chunk of the budget earmarked for the visit of the leader. This practice is condemned because it has no direct bearing on the wellbeing of the masses. The foregoing stanza is replete with tropes of mendacity. The radio jingles, TV announcements, newstalks and editorials, among others only hero-worship a megalomaniac leader.

The city practically turns riotous at the visit of a political actor. Images of disorder are evident in the fourth stanza:

Sirens

Hallucination

Fascination

Dark Mercedes

Trepidation

Tinted glasses

Imagination

Coat of Arms in front

Coat of Arms behind

Flags behind

Flags everywhere

Entourage cars (p. 41).

The foregoing contains symbols of hegemony with which the people are intimidated to submission, molested and subjugated. There is nothing to indicate sanity in a typical environment where a leader pays a state visit. It is always an exhibitionist atmosphere of power and force. Sirens blare to no end to scare the people, as high-class vehicles of different shades form a long motorcade. The image evoked is that of extravagance as funds that could be channelled towards people-oriented projects are frittered away in the guise of preparing for a leader's visit. The most pathetic imagery in the poem is the scene where the people are emotionally molested by the men of power. Vehicles are made to come to a halt because a man of power is around:

Taxis, brake and park!

Lories, brake and park!

Bolekaja, break and park!

Ndi private, break and park!

Inaga, brake and park

Bicycles, brake and park! (p. 41).

There is clearly an imagery of subjugation in the foregoing lines. The people feel intimidated by the sheer appurtenances of power at the disposal of visiting political leader, reinforcing the inequalities in the country. Thus, the people live in awe of the might of his office which is literally unleashed on them. The repetition of "brake and park" carries a note of finality. The people are coerced to park until the long and expensive motorcade of the visiting leader clears out of the way.

It is ironic that a leader who should serve the people compels them to sacrifice their time for him. It is even more ironic that despite the noisy reception, the visiting leader only makes empty promises aimed at hoodwinking the people:

“My government will ...”

Applause

“My government will ...”

Applause

“My government will ...” (p. 42)

The foregoing is a sarcastic recreation of the clichéous, vain promises dished out to the masses by government officials. The promises are all ironies as none of them are fulfilled. They are, at best, used to impress the people for whom they have no genuine developmental plans. In the end, the persona uses three synonymous noun phrases to illustrate the aftermath of the political visit: “Faintness/stillness/Blankness” (p. 42). The people would return to the deleterious status quo – where there is lack of government presence. They live on their own and face the harsh realities of life without any government intervention.

The commitment of Nwachukwu-Agbada to social justice is further illustrated in his “What the Seer Said,” a dramatic poem which recreates an interaction between the poet’s persona and an imaginary seer about injustice in the land. The tone of the poem is pessimistic as the seer gives a damning verdict – ruling out the possibilities of justice served by those in the judicial sector of the country. The subject of justice is symbolised using use of “Niger”. The seer dismisses the possibility of the Niger flowing in the land again:

Seer, seer

say, will the Niger flow through this area again

flow?
No, son
The Niger's drowned, drained
droughted, dead
left lingering in an arid area, acrid
still reeling on rotted crooked rails (p. 15).

The mood of the poem, however, is gloomy. There seems to be no future for the justice system, and the common man mostly affected by the social injustice in the land. The poet's persona is apparently concerned with the state of corruption in the justice administration of his country. He seeks to know what the future holds for the justice sector of his country. The interrogative expression in the second line clearly illustrates the commitment of the persona to an egalitarian society. The response of the seer is further laced in tropes of fatalism. First, the justice system is described as "drowned" hence it would not come back to life again. Second, it is "drained" hence nothing remains out of it. Also, it is "droughted" and "dead" hence should be forgotten.

Images of deterioration dot the entire poem. Where the "Niger" used to flow is now "arid area/acrid/Still reeling on rotted crooked rails" (p. 15). The use of the adjective "arid" symbolises barrenness just as "acrid" illustrates the harshness of the terrain where justice is administered. The human factors implicated in the saga include the lawyers and judges:

The coats of our illustrious lawyers
The gowns of our prodigious prosecutors
The wigs of our gorgeous judges
Have drained all the water, drained all our water
Through slimy channels of due purchase of land

Leaving us only tired tributaries of tribunal-truth

Their truth mere tales at

Meant to tickle old tangle of ties (p. 15).

The foregoing lines are both sarcastic and ironic. First the lawyers are described as ‘illustrious’, a trope qualifying them in excellent terms. Yet the “coats” of these lawyers lack the “water” of truth and justice. There are “prodigious prosecutors” that ordinarily should be models in the temple of justice. They are however compromised as their “gowns” are “drained” of the water of justice. Ironically, there are judges described in impressive terms as “gorgeous” whose “wigs” unfortunately lack the “water” of justice. They are condemned by the poet’s persona as those who pervert justice. The said characters are complicit in the flawed justice system of the Nigerian nation.

Since these characters have colluded to drain the nation of the Niger flow, what is now left of the country are “tired tributaries of tribunal truth”, a metaphor for technical facts that have replaced the truth. By so doing, they take the land for granted as the persona views the truth as “mere tales to dark hour” told to idiots. The metaphor of “mere takes at dark hour” is that of painted lies presented as truth which undermine social justice.

While men at the temple of justice struggle to manipulate the truth at “dark hours”, the persona reveals that the truth lies “trusted up/like an uncombed hair full of lice, “ (p.15), implying that the truth requires no support or collaboration. It is always firmed up for all to see. The simile in the latter line is imperative because the truth needs no beautification or decoration to come out as truth. On the other hand, lies are couched in beautiful colours to sound as truth.

The tone of the poem remains a depressed one from beginning to end. Having analysed the perversion of justice by the revered custodians of the law, the poem expresses hopelessness at the

likelihood of justice returning in the land. Once again, he asks the seer what the future holds in stock for the justice system in the country:

Seer, seer

Say, will the Niger flow through this area again?

Glow?

No, son

Not on soils soiled by a tissue of lies (p. 15).

The alliteration in the last line reinforces the reason for the disappearance of the Niger. The “soil” has been “soiled” by “a tissue of lies” by the custodians of justice in the land. No nation thrives in an atmosphere of injustice, or where the weak are not protected. There is no genuine nation-building where the judiciary is weak, timid and corrupt. This is the crux of Nwachukwu-Agbada’s “What the Seer Said.”

Conclusion

Commitment in literature is a conscious engagement of writers with the socio-political, cultural and economic realities of their environment. These writers use literature as a tool for advocacy and social transformation. Commitment in modern African literature began with cultural activism associated with the colonial era and progressed to the disillusionment of the post-independence era. Commitment in literature is a veritable ideology that highlights a writer’s belief in an egalitarian society. It has become a means through which writers participate in nation-building. Commitment in art has established writers as critical thinkers, philosophers and clairvoyants of their society. Achebe published *A Man of the People* and shortly afterwards, Nigeria’s first military coup took place.

In his *Prayer Beads of the Silent Suppliant* (2005), J.O. J. Nwachukwu-Agbada, a professor of Literature expands the epistemic boundaries of literature of commitment in Africa. The collection has 78 poems written on varied issues in Africa. The paper chose four verses from the anthology due to the constraints of time and space – poems which profoundly justify the poet as a committed writer. The Reflectionist theory – the idea that literature is a reflection of the social, political, cultural, economic and ethical realities of the society that produced it – has been applied in the analysis of the poems. The research findings highlight Nwachukwu-Agbada as a socially committed writer who makes extensive use of the literary devices of metaphor, rhetorical question, parallelism, irony and sarcasm in art to describe the inept leadership of the Nigerian society, which is directly responsible for the social inequalities in the land.

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